

Role of Dietary Fibre and fluid Intake on Constipation Relief

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ABSTRACT

Constipation is a common gastrointestinal disorder characterized by infrequent bowel movements, hard stools, and difficulty in defecation. Dietary habits, particularly low fibre intake and inadequate fluid consumption are major contributing factors. This paper explains the physiological role of dietary fibre and fluids in bowel regulation and highlights their combined importance in preventing and relieving constipation. Evidence suggests that adequate intake of fibre along with sufficient fluids improves stool bulk consistency and intestinal motility, making them primary non-pharmacological interventions for constipation management.

Keywords: *Dietary fiber, Fluid intake, Constipation, Strategies*

Introduction:-

Constipation is defined as a condition characterized by infrequent or difficulty in evacuation of stools. Constipation affects individuals of all age groups and is especially common among children, pregnant women and the elderly. It is often caused by poor dietary habits, sedentary life style, dehydration and excessive consumption of refined foods. Constipation can be accompanied by various symptoms which include hard stools, straining while passing stools, sensation of anorectal blockage, incomplete evacuation and abdominal discomfort. Constipation occurs when stool moves too slowly through the colon, becoming hard, dry and difficult to pass often due to low fibre or fluid intake, lack of exercise or change in routine with symptoms like infrequent or painful bowel movements.

Constipation is one of the major gastrointestinal disorders. The definition of constipation points to a decreased number of defecations per week, as well as multiple symptoms such as sensation of incomplete evacuation, abdominal

bloating, straining, elongated or failed attempts to defecate, hard stools and necessity of digital disimpaction. Constipation due to its etiology, is commonly divided into two groups, primary and secondary. Primary constipation includes constipation predominant irritable bowel syndrome, functional constipation, slow transit constipation like myopathy, neuropathy and functional defecation disorders. Secondary constipation may be a result of metabolic disorders. It decreases life quality among patients as they suffer from both physical symptoms and psychological distress. Chronic constipation limits work productivity and social activity. It has a significant impact on quality of life.

Constipation can be occasional chronic and causes range from a sedentary life style to gastrointestinal conditions. But in almost every case of constipation food is an important factor; Diet plays an important role as a modifiable life style factor that can affect the onset and progression of constipation.

Fibre is a major component of foods that relieve constipation and of poop itself. Fibre supports the microbiome: the healthy balance of bacteria in the digestive tract. Fibre also helps gut motility: the coordination of muscle contractions in the intestines that push food along the digestive process. There are two types of fibre found in food; soluble fibre and insoluble fibre. Foods rich in one or both kinds can relieve both occasional and chronic constipation. Insoluble fibre is roughage which our body cannot breakdown in digestion. So, it leaves the pretty much as it goes in, for example skins and seeds of fruits and vegetables, popcorn, leafy greens, nuts, dried fruit. Soluble fibre on the other hand is a type of fibre that dissolves in water. When dissolved in water in the digestive tract, soluble fibre forms a gel that adds bulk. The gel also acts as a natural stool softener making bowel movements easier and more comfortable to pass. Soluble fibres can be found in whole grains, apples, bananas, oatmeal, cooked vegetables. So one should eat more fibre to relieve constipation. Experts also stress the importance of adequate hydration. Water is essential in helping fibre work its magic. On the other hand high fat foods can contribute to constipation. Again the process of eating stimulates the digestive system end to end so at least theoretically keeping a regular daily meal schedule could support regular bowel movements. Feeling constipated gives a huge blocker feel.

Hence, constipation is a common digestive issue that affects individual across all age groups. This situation is uncomfortable or frustrating, but dietary changes can help prevent it. If the constipation is left untreated it leads to further complications like anal fissures, faecal impaction and haemorrhoids. Thus by including food for constipation relief in daily routine one can improve digestion, promote regular bowel movement and alleviate pain.

Table No.- 1
Prevalence of Constipation

Population Group	Prevalence
Global Population	14-20%
Women Vs Men	2-3 times higher in women
Older adults (>60 Yrs)	30-40%
Children (global)	3-10%
India (Community Studies)	16-28 %

Table No.- 2
Dietary and lifestyle risk factors for constipation

Factor	Observation
Low fibre intake (<15g/day)	Strongly associated constipation
Recommended fibre intake	25-38 g/day
Low fluid intake (<1.5 L/day)	Increases stool hardness
Physical inactivity	20-30% higher risk
High Refined food intake	Increased prevalence

Table No.- 3
Clinical Characteristics of constipation

Clinical feature	Frequency
<3 bowel movements/week	Diagnostic criterion
Hard Stools	60-70%
Excessive straining	>75%
Functional Constipation	>90% cases

Table No. 4
Public Health Significance

Parameter	Data
Primary case visits	5-10% due to constipation
Quality of life	Significantly reduced
Health Burden	Increased laxative use and costs
Global importance	Common functional GI disorder

Discussion:

The results demonstrate that constipation is a widespread condition influenced by complex interaction of dietary, lifestyle, physiological and demographic factors. The higher prevalence observed among women may be attributed to hormonal influences, slower colonic transit time and psychosocial factors. The increased burden among older adults can be explained by age related decline in gastro intestinal motility, reduced physical activity, lower dietary fibre intake and poly pharmacy.

Dietary fibre plays a central role in bowel regularity by increasing stool bulk and water holding capacity, thereby facilitating intestinal transit. The strong association between low fibre intake and constipation observed in this analysis supports existing nutritional recommendation emphasizing whole grains fruits, vegetables and legumes. Similarly inadequate fluid intake contributes to stool dehydration and hardness, further aggravating constipation.

Urbanisation and changing dietary patterns characterized by increased consumption of refined and processed foods may explain the higher prevalence reported in Indian urban populations. In children, behavioural factors such as stool withholding, poor toilets habits and low intake of fibre rich foods are important contributors.

The predominance of functional constipation indicates that most cases can be effectively managed through dietary modifications, adequate hydration and life style changes rather than pharmacological interventions from a public health perspective. Constipation significantly affects quality of life and increases health care utilization reinforcing the need for preventive strategies. World Health Organisation

recognize functional gastrointestinal disorders, including constipation as common yet under addressed health concerns.

Conclusion:

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of nutrition education, promotion of fibre rich diets, adequate fluid intake and physical activity as key strategies for constipation prevention and management.

References:

1. Suares NC, Ford AC, Prevalence of chronic constipation: systematic review. Am J Gastroenterol, 2011.
2. Higgins PD, Johanson JF. Epidemiology of Constipation. Am J Gastroenterol. 2004.
3. Bharucha AE, etal. American Gastro enterological Association technical review on constipation Gastroenterology 2013.
4. Tabbers MM, etal. Evaluation and treatment of functional constipation in children J pediatr Gastroenterol Nutr. 2014
5. Ghoshal UC, etal. Epidemiology of constipation in India. Indian J Gastroentrol 2012.
6. Institute of Medicine, Dietary References Intakes for Fibre, 2005.
7. Rome IV Criteria, Functional gastrointestinal disorders. 2016.
8. <https://peping.in>
9. [https:// www.narayanhealth.org](https://www.narayanhealth.org)
10. [https:// www.hopkinsmedicine.org](https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org)
11. [https:// www.sciencedirect.com](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

